

**PROSTHETICS WITH IMMEDIATE PROSTHESES IN
ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY INDICATIONS FOR THE INSTALLATION
OF AN IMMEDIATE PROSTHESIS**

(literary review)

Salohiddinov Mirzabek Bahodir ugli

Irgashev Shoxrux Xasanovich

Samarkand State Medical University

Annotation: The fixation of the structure is carried out by small metal hooks.

If necessary, a removable immediate prosthesis can be attached directly to the implant. The basic components of the product are acrylic or nylon. A very soft and elastic material of the immediate prosthesis is selected, to which the patient quickly adapts. There is no long-term habituation to the foreign body in the mouth, there is no discomfort or rubbing of the soft tissues.

The color of the base is clearly selected to match the color of the gingival tissue, so that it is almost impossible to visually distinguish between the temporary structure and the natural tooth. When an immediate prosthesis is performed in the anterior part of the jaw, the patient is not embarrassed and the aesthetics of the natural dentition are maintained.

It is important to remember that the main purpose of an immediate prosthesis is a temporary replacement of a removed tooth. It is not particularly durable, since the design does not provide for long-term wear.

In what cases do they resort to immediate prostheses:

- Temporary replacement of one or more teeth;
- * An intermediate stage in the implantation process that allows waiting for the implant to fully take root;
- * Replacement of the patient's teeth until the production of a permanent orthopedic structure;

- * Effective protection against thinning of the jaw bone tissue;
- Restoration of functionality of the dentition after tooth extraction;
- Prevention of facial asymmetry;
- * Protection against the displacement of adjacent teeth towards the formed cavity;
- * Prevention of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract associated with poor-quality mastication of food at the time of temporary absence of teeth.

Contraindications for the installation of immediate prostheses

As with any prosthetic system, it cannot be installed in case of inflammatory processes in the oral cavity in the acute phase.

Treatment of caries is also necessary in advance.

Such structures are not suitable in cases where significant abnormalities in the formation of the bite are diagnosed.

Also, in rare cases, individual intolerance to the materials used in the manufacture of the product is possible.

Types of immediate prostheses

The manufacture of immediate prostheses can have different types of structures. This is necessary in order to take into account all the needs of the patient: temporary prostheses can replace a different number of teeth, which also means different in different degrees of strength and types of fixation. In modern dentistry, three types of immediate prostheses have been developed.

The butterfly design, which gets its name from its similarity to insect wings, is the most popular solution. The hooks resemble the shape of a butterfly and have special structures for a firm attachment to adjacent teeth. "Butterfly" temporarily replaces one or two missing teeth.

A partial prosthesis is indicated when four or more teeth have been removed. The structure has a large base and is fixed with metal or plastic hooks. The

installation of this option is necessary to maintain a full-fledged chewing function.

A complete immediate prosthesis is a replacement of the entire row of teeth. Unlike other types, it can be used not only as a temporary solution, but also as a permanent one. An artificial row can be fixed on the cap of the implant. It can be installed simultaneously on both the upper and lower jaw.

Stages of manufacturing an immediate prosthesis

First of all, the doctor and the patient decide on the type of material. Acrylic models are considered a universal option. They have a wide range of applications, a relatively strong structure and low cost. But acrylic often causes allergic reactions.

Nylon products are more expensive, but do not pose any risk of allergies. The service life is very long - up to 24 months. After that, the structure collapses due to constant chewing loads.

The main stages of immediate prosthesis:

- * Consultation with an orthopedist;
- * The doctor determines possible contraindications for installation;
- * Professional hygienic cleaning of the oral cavity;
- Production of a plaster cast;
- Creation of a prosthesis according to individual parameters.

The manufacture of products for temporary prostheses does not take much time. After 1-2 days, the structures are ready for installation. They are very easy to care for daily and do not require special skills or the use of special tools. In case of wear, they can be promptly replaced with a similar type of prosthesis.

To conclude: prosthetics with immediate prostheses is convenient and comfortable in prosthetics with partial adentia.

Literature:

1. Ризаев Ж. А., Ахмедов А. А. ОСНОВЫ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН НА ОСНОВЕ РАЗВИТИЯ

ОБЩЕЙ ВРАЧЕБНОЙ ПРАКТИКИ //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3.

2. Ризаев Ж. А., Ахмедов А. А. GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL MEDICAL PRACTICE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN TO IMPROVE DENTAL CARE //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3.

3. Astanovich A. D. A. et al. The State of Periodontal Tissues in Athletes Engaged in Cyclic Sports //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – С. 235-241.

4. Alimjanovich R. J., Astanovich A. A. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОГО ПОДХОДА ДЛЯ УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ЕЕ КАЧЕСТВА //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 8. – №. 4.

5. Ортикова Н. Глобализация биоэтики в период пандемии COVID-19 //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/S. – С. 677-682.

6. Ортикова Н. Влияние психоэмоционального напряжения детей на состояние здоровья полости рта //Общество и инновации. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 7/S. – С. 328-333.

7. Ортикова Н. Х., Ризаев Ж. А., Мелибаев Б. А. ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПОСТРОЕНИЯ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ПРИЕМА ПАЦИЕНТОВ ДЕТСКОГО ВОЗРАСТА //EDITOR COORDINATOR. – 2021. – С. 554.

8. Ортикова Н. Тенденция эффективности профилактических мероприятий путем коррекции психологического стресса у детей на

стоматологическом приёме //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 181-189.

9. Fakhridin C., Shokhruh S., Nilufar I. ENDOKANAL PIN-KONSTRUKSIYALARNI ISHLATISHDA ASORATLAR VA XATOLAR TAHLILI //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 1.

10. Shoxrux S., Shoxrux I., Faxriddin C. PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF ORAL INFECTIONS IN DENTURE WEARERS //International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education. – 2022. – Т. 14. – №. 4.

11. Xusanovich C. F. COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHESIS SUPPORTED BY IMPLANTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 127-133.

12. Xusanovich C. F. et al. PROSTHETICS A COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHESIS BASED ON IMPLANTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 122-126.

13. Sevinch E., Zarafruz B. ETIOLOGICAL TREATMENT FEATURES INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASE //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 03. – С. 241-246.

14. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF COPD IN ELDERLY PATIENTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 05. – С. 363-368.

15. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. STUDY THE EFFECT OF HYGIENIC CARE ON THE MICROBIAL LANDSCAPE OF THE ORAL

CAVITY IN PATIENTS USING COMBINED SPLINTING STRUCTURES WITH MODERATE PERIODONTITIS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 02. – C. 50-55.

16. Sevinch E., Qobilovna B. Z. A STUDY ON THE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL STATE OF ORAL ORGAN TISSUES DURING THE USE OF NON-REMOVABLE ORTHODONTIC STRUCTURES //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 03. – C. 247-253.

17. Shaximardonova E. S., Kobilovna B. Z. RED LICHEN PLANUS OF THE ORAL MUCOSA AND ITS CLINICAL ANALYSIS OF A PATIENT WITH, ASSOCIATED WITH THE EPSTEIN—BARR VIRUS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 01. – C. 272-279.

18. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. STUDY OF CHANGES IN THE ORAL CAVITY IN ENDOCRINE DISEASES //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 05. – C. 357-362.

19. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. SMARTBURS II—A REVIEW OF THE ADVANTAGES OF SMART BOR //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 02. – C. 56-60.